

CHECKING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF APPLYING THE AUTHOR'S MODEL FOR DEVELOPING SENIOR STUDENTS' RESEARCH COMPETENCE IN PHYSICS

Article's purpose. The article is aimed at presenting the results of the forming stage of the psychological and pedagogical research on determining the effectiveness of applying the author's model of developing senior students research competence in the process of teaching Physics.

Methodology. Analysis of the legal documents of Ukraine, standards, syllabi in Physics, textbooks and manuals; synthesis of the present approaches in the theory and practice of teaching Physics to solving the problem of developing lyceum students' research competence in Physics; observing the process of teaching Physics to lyceum students in order to determine its regularities and possibilities of improvement in the direction of forming the research competence; diagnosing the level of development of lyceum students' research competence; testing; evaluation of learning outcomes; testing the suggested methodology; pedagogical experiment; methods of mathematical statistics at the stage of processing and summarizing the results of the pedagogical experiment and formulating conclusions to confirm the scientific novelty and practical significance of the study.

Scientific novelty. Analysis of materials for molding and control experiments using criteria F-Fisher, Pearson (χ^2) were represented; identification of active directions for the further development of the theory of forming and developing lyceum students research competence in the process of teaching Physics was shown; transformation of the relationship between the theoretical and empirical approaches for practical application in education in Physics was presented.

Conclusion. The results of the pedagogical experiment showed the effectiveness of the suggested theoretical and methodological grounds for developing research competence on the basis of competence, activity, personality-oriented and technological approaches, as well as pedagogical expediency and effectiveness of the methodical system of development of research competence of students of the lyceum of natural sciences and mathematics of the direction of differentiation in the study of Physics.

Key words: research competence, methodical system of forming research competence, educational and methodical complex.

Setting the problem. Checking the effectiveness of the methodical system for developing the senior students' research competence in the process of teaching Physics is a complex process of scientific and pedagogical activity aimed at improving the existing system of education, training and developing young generation. Such testing is a complicated way of creative searches in the process of completing a series of interrelated stages, the optimal sequence of which is due to the idea of the psychological and pedagogical study aimed at investigating the problem of developing the students' research competence in the process of teaching Physics. As a result, we are to obtain experimental data pointing to the gaps in the process of forming a person-researcher in comprehensive school [1; 2].

Analysis of the latest researches and publications. The problem of forming and developing senior pupils' and students' research competence is at the initial stage of its solution. Its various aspects were considered in the works of Ukrainian and foreign scientists, in particular: the essence of the competence approach in education (N. Bibik, T. Ivanova, I. Yermakov, O. Ovcharuk, O. Pometun, A. Khutorskoy, S. Shishov, et al); the essence and structure of the concepts of «competence» and «being competent» (N. Bibik, S. Bondar, I. Zymnya, O. Pometun, O. Savchenko, J. Raven, A. Khutorskoy et al); general bases for implementing the competence approach in secondary schools (V. Luhovy, O. Lyashenko, O. Savchenko, V. Sharko, A. Khutorskoy et al); methodological foundations for developing pupils' educational and cognitive competences (L. Blahodarenko, Ye. Bondarevs'ka, V. Krayevs'ky, M. Shut, I. Yakimans'ka et al); psychological bases of developing educational and cognitive competences (G. Ball, V. Davydov, B. El'konin, I. Zymnya et al).

Setting the aims of the article. The article is aimed at presenting the results of the forming stage of psychological and pedagogical research on determining the effectiveness of applying the author's model for developing senior pupils' research competence in the process of teaching Physics.

Presenting the main material of the investigation with full grounding of the obtained scientific results. Realizing the stating (2005–2009) and searching (2009–2013) stages of the psychological and pedagogical investigation made it possible to find out the peculiarities of conducting the educational process in Physics for senior pupils concerning the organization of the senior pupils' research activity. The obtained data were used while implementing the forming stage of the psycho-pedagogical research by developing, correcting and introducing the author's model of the research competence development in the educational process in Physics in senior forms [3; 4; 5; 6].

The context of our study was grounded on the definition of the research competence as a system of students' abilities to conduct an active searching activity aimed at solving various problems in the research process. The structure of the research competence is presented by four components: *motivational, operational, reflexive and technological*. We measured the formed stage of each component of the senior students' research competence by three levels: low, medium and high.

At the forming stage of the psychological and pedagogical research it was extremely important to maintain the purity of the experiment. So, in the period from 2013 to 2017 we worked with three streams of senior pupils – the first stream (2013–2015), the second stream (2014–2016) and the third stream (2015–2017) (see Table 1). A number of comprehensive schools of Sumy and Chernihiv regions were selected as the experimental base of the forming stage.

Table 1

Quantitative data of streaming the respondents at the forming stage

Academic year	10 th form (forms number / students number)		11 th form (forms number / students number)	
	Town	Village and settlement	Town	Village and settlement
2013/2014 academic year	12 / 264	10 / 113		
2014/2015 academic year	12 / 231	10 / 109	12 / 264	10 / 113
2015/2016 academic year	12 / 241	10 / 136	12 / 231	10 / 109
2016/2017 academic year			12 / 241	10 / 136
	736	358		
Total	1094			

We calculated the minimum number of respondents provided that the error of the results should be less than 5% ($E = 0,05$). Using the expression (1)

$$n = \frac{t^2 pq}{E^2}, \quad (1)$$

where n – quantity of the obligatory respondents; t – function argument $F(t)$, which value is equal to the ahead determined probability P (value of t is calculated according to table 5 [7, 204-206] of the function value $F(t)$ at different values of t); p – probability of emerging event; $q = 1 - p$ – probability of the opposite event (since values p and q are unknown we assumed that $p = q = 0,5$; while multiplication product $p \cdot q$ will be maximum and the artificial value n will be a little overestimated but quite reliable); E – error of the obtained results [7, 101], and the table of function values $F(t)$ (it was taken into account that when $P = F(t) = 0,95$ $t = 1,96$ [7, 205]), we obtained the necessary number of respondents: $n = 384,16$.

For each of the three streams, the forming stage of the psychological and pedagogical research was carried out in three steps: 1) the stating testing was conducted in the stream at the beginning of the 10th form in order to identify the level of the respondents' research competence; 2) on receiving the results and processing them we identified the control (CG) and experimental (EG) groups in the stream, began to appropiate the author's pedagogical model for developing senior students' research competence in the process of teaching Physics; 3) at the end of testing the author's model (end of the 11th form for the stream) we repeated testing the control and experimental groups.

After the final testing at this stage of the psychological and pedagogical research grounding on the methods of mathematical statistics the analysis of the author's approach influence on the level of senior pupils' research competence in the process of teaching Physics was carried out.

The quantitative distribution of students by control and experimental samples is given in Table 2.

Table 2

Quantitative distribution of pupils by the control and experiment samples

10 th form			
Town		Village and urban type settlement	
CG	EG	CG	EG
354	382	170	188
736		358	
Total in CG		524	
Total in EG		570	
Total		1094	

The distribution of respondents by levels according to the components of the research competence and the total distribution received by us at the beginning of the forming stage is given in Tables 3–7.

Table 3

Distributing respondents by the level of motivational component of research competence (initial test)

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	50 (14%)	201 (57%)	103 (29%)	20 (12%)	104 (61%)	46 (27%)	70 (13%)	305 (58%)	149 (29%)	524
EG	46 (12%)	233 (61%)	103 (27%)	25 (13%)	103 (55%)	60 (32%)	71 (12%)	336 (59%)	163 (29%)	570

Table 4

Distributing respondents by the level of operational component of research competence (initial test)

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	42 (12%)	203 (57%)	109 (31%)	16 (9%)	56 (33%)	98 (58%)	58 (11%)	259 (49%)	207 (40%)	524
EG	36 (9%)	198 (52%)	148 (39%)	19 (10%)	57 (30%)	112 (60%)	55 (10%)	255 (45%)	260 (45%)	570

Table 5

Distributing respondents by the level of reflexive component of research competence (initial test)

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	46 (13%)	202 (57%)	106 (30%)	18 (11%)	80 (47%)	72 (42%)	64 (12%)	282 (54%)	178 (34%)	524
EG	41 (11%)	216 (57%)	125 (32%)	22 (12%)	80 (43%)	86 (45%)	63 (11%)	296 (52%)	211 (37%)	570

Table 6

**Distributing respondents by the level of technological component
of research competence (initial test)**

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	76 (21%)	234 (66%)	44 (13%)	65 (38%)	97 (57%)	8 (5%)	141 (27%)	331 (63%)	52 (10%)	524
EG	70 (18%)	241 (63%)	71 (19%)	60 (32%)	86 (46%)	42 (22%)	130 (23%)	327 (57%)	113 (20%)	570

Averaging the indicators by the components of research competence allows us to get the general distribution of respondents according to the levels of research competence (Table 7).

Table 7

Distributing respondents by the levels of research competence (initial test)

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	52 (15%)	210 (59%)	92 (26%)	35 (20%)	81 (48%)	54 (32%)	87 (17%)	291 (56%)	146 (27%)	524
EG	53 (14%)	223 (58%)	106 (28%)	36 (19%)	77 (41%)	75 (40%)	89 (15%)	300 (53%)	181 (32%)	570

At the end of the forming stage control tests were conducted on each stream (Tables 8–11).

Table 8

**Distributing respondents by the level of motivational component
of research competence (final test)**

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	48 (14%)	215 (60%)	91 (26%)	20 (12%)	110 (65%)	40 (23%)	68 (13%)	325 (62%)	131 (25%)	524
EG	67 (18%)	259 (68%)	56 (14%)	24 (13%)	120 (64%)	44 (23%)	91 (16%)	379 (66%)	100 (18%)	570

Table 9

**Distributing respondents by the level of operational component
of research competence (final test)**

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	45 (13%)	187 (53%)	122 (34%)	12 (7%)	87 (51%)	71 (42%)	57 (11%)	274 (52%)	193 (37%)	524
EG	49 (13%)	245 (64%)	88 (23%)	18 (10%)	69 (37%)	101 (53%)	67 (12%)	314 (55%)	189 (33%)	570

Table 10

Distributing respondents by the level of reflexive component of research competence (final test)

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	51 (14%)	204 (58%)	99 (28%)	14 (8%)	101 (60%)	55 (32%)	65 (12%)	305 (58%)	154 (30%)	524
EG	68 (18%)	266 (70%)	48 (12%)	32 (17%)	86 (46%)	70 (37%)	100 (17%)	352 (62%)	118 (21%)	570

Table 11

**Distributing respondents by the level of technological component
of research competence (final test)**

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	71 (20%)	247 (70%)	36 (10%)	63 (37%)	102 (60%)	5 (3%)	134 (25%)	349 (67%)	41 (8%)	524
EG	97 (25%)	256 (67%)	29 (8%)	75 (40%)	83 (44%)	30 (16%)	172 (30%)	339 (60%)	59 (10%)	570

Averaging the indicators of research competence components allows us to get the total distribution of respondents by the levels of research competence in the final test (Table 12).

Table 12

Distributing respondents by the levels of research competence (final test)

Group	Town			Village and urban type settlement			Total number			Total
	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
CG	54 (15%)	213 (60%)	87 (25%)	27 (16%)	100 (59%)	43 (25%)	81 (16%)	313 (60%)	130 (24%)	524
EG	70 (18%)	257 (68%)	55 (14%)	37 (20%)	90 (48%)	61 (32%)	107 (19%)	347 (61%)	116 (20%)	570

To identify statistically significant differences in the levels of respondents' research competence in experimental and control samples we use the method of checking statistical hypotheses. The experimental data from Tables 3–12 are used to test the zero and alternative hypothesis by Pearson criterion (χ^2), as follows: 1) both samples are random; 2) the samples are independent and the members from each of the samples are independent of each other; 3) the scale of measurement is a scale of titles with 3 categories.

Let us formulate the main H_0 and alternative H_1 hypotheses.

Zero hypothesis H_0 : the probability of entering students of the control and experimental samples in each of the categories i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) is equal, that is $H_0: p_{1i} = p_{2i}$ and the higher level of the experimental group is due to random factors.

Alternative hypothesis H_1 : $p_{1i} \neq p_{2i}$ for at least one of $i = 3$ categories, that is this higher level is grounded by the results of the suggested methods.

We use the two-sided Pearson criterion (χ^2) for checking the hypothesis of the investigation [8]. Taking into account that the number of categories $c = 3$, according to expression (2) we calculate the value of statistics of criterion T of the researched random value:

$$T = \frac{1}{n_1 \cdot n_2} \sum_{i=1}^c \frac{(n_1 \cdot Q_{2i} - n_2 \cdot Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}, \quad (2)$$

where Q_{1i} and Q_{2i} ($i = 1, 2, 3$) – the number of students of experimental and control forms that got into the i -th category. By the Table for the number of degrees of freedom $\nu = 3 - 1 = 2$ and $\alpha = 0,05$ is the level of significance we find the critical value T: $T_{\text{crit}} = 6$.

We found statistically significant differences in the experimental and control samples as well as the differences in the control sample before and after the forming experiment. The results of calculations of statistics t of the presented samples are given in Tables 13–16.

Based on the data given in Table 13 we can conclude: the obtained data of checking the statistical significance of differences in the levels of the motivational component of research competence (initial test) make grounds for adopting the zero hypothesis, which is the confirmation of the same level of the component of respondents' research competence of the CG and EG ($T_{it} = 0,200686 < T_{\text{crit}} = 6$);

the obtained data of checking the statistical significance of the differences in the levels of the motivational component of research competence make grounds for rejecting the zero hypothesis and adopting the alternative one which confirms the fact that the levels of the motivational component of the respondents' research competence are different and this difference became possible due to applying the author's model in the educational process ($T_{it} = 9,712247 > T_{\text{crit}} = 6$).

Table 13

**Checking statistical significance of differences in levels
of research competence motivational component**

initial test				
	H	M	L	T _{it}
n ₁	570			
Q _{2i} (KΓ)	70	305	149	
n ₂	524			
Q _{1i} (EΓ)	71	336	163	
n ₁ Q _{2i} - n ₂ Q _{1i}	2696	-2214	-482	
Q _{1i} + Q _{2i}	141	641	312	
$\frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$	51549,05	7647,108	744,6282	0,200686
final test				
	H	M	L	T _{ft}
n ₁	570			
Q _{2i} (KΓ)	68	325	131	
n ₂	524			
Q _{1i} (EΓ)	91	379	100	
n ₁ Q _{2i} - n ₂ Q _{1i}	-8924	-13346	22270	
Q _{1i} + Q _{2i}	159	704	231	
$\frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$	500866,5	253005,3	2146982	9,712247

Based on the data given in Table 14 we can conclude: the obtained data of verifying the statistical significance of the differences in the levels of the operational component of the research competence (initial test) make grounds for adopting the zero hypothesis which is the confirmation of the same level of the component of the respondents' research competence of the CG and EG (T_{it} = 4,199001 < T_{crit} = 6); the obtained data of verifying the statistical significance of differences in the levels of the operational component of the research competence do not make grounds for rejecting the zero hypothesis which is the confirmation of the same level of the operational component of the senior pupils' research competence of the control and experimental samples (T_{ft} = 1,638135 < T_{crit} = 6).

Table 14

**Checking statistical significance of differences in levels
of research competence operational component**

initial test				
	H	M	L	T _{it}
n ₁	570			
Q _{2i} (KΓ)	58	259	207	
n ₂	524			
Q _{1i} (EΓ)	55	255	260	
n ₁ Q _{2i} - n ₂ Q _{1i}	4240	14010	-18250	
Q _{1i} + Q _{2i}	113	514	467	
$\frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$	159093,8	381867,9	713195,9	4,199001
final test				
	H	M	L	T _{ft}
n ₁	570			
Q _{2i} (KΓ)	57	274	193	
n ₂	524			
Q _{1i} (EΓ)	67	314	189	
n ₁ Q _{2i} - n ₂ Q _{1i}	-2618	-8356	10974	
Q _{1i} + Q _{2i}	124	588	382	
$\frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$	55273,58	118746,1	315258,3	1,638135

Based on the data given in Table 15 we can conclude: the obtained data of checking the statistical significance of differences in the levels of the reflexive component of the research competence (initial test) make grounds for accepting the zero hypothesis which is the confirmation of the same level of the component of the respondents' research competence of the CG and EG ($T_{it} = 1,214421 < T_{crit} = 6$); the obtained data of verifying the statistical significance of differences in the levels of the reflexive component of the research competence make grounds for rejecting the zero hypothesis and accepting the alternative one which is a confirmation of the fact that the levels of the reflexive component of the respondents' research competence are different and this difference became possible due to applying the author's model in the educational process ($T_{ft} = 13,64113 > T_{crit} = 6$).

Table 15

**Checking statistical significance of differences in levels
of research competence reflexive component**

initial test				
	H	M	L	T_{it}
n_1	570			
$Q_{2i} (KG)$	64	282	178	
n_2	524			
$Q_{1i} (EG)$	63	296	211	
$n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i}$	3468	5636	-9104	
$Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}$	127	578	389	
$\frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$	94700,98	54955,88	213066,4	1,214421
final test				
	H	M	L	T_{ft}
n_1	570			
$Q_{2i} (KG)$	65	305	154	
n_2	524			
$Q_{1i} (EG)$	100	352	118	
$n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i}$	-15350	-10598	25948	
$Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}$	165	657	272	
$\frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$	1428015	170955,3	2475363	13,64113

Grounding on the data presented in Table 16 we can conclude: the obtained data of checking the statistical significance of the differences in the levels of the technological component of the research competence (initial test) make grounds for adopting the zero hypothesis, which confirms the same level of component of the research competence of respondents of the control group and the experimental group ($T_{it} = 5,155162 < T_{crit} = 6$); the obtained data of checking the statistical significance of differences in the levels of the technological component of the research competence make grounds for rejecting the zero hypothesis and adopting the alternative one which confirms that the levels of the technological component of the respondents' research competence are different and this difference became possible due to applying the author's model in the educational process ($T_{ft} = 6,181045 > T_{crit} = 6$).

Conclusion of the research and perspectives for further investigation in the field. For each component of the senior students' research competence in Physics (motivational, operational, reflexive and technological), we suggested an alternative hypothesis, which, in general, allows us to speak about the effectiveness of the developed pedagogical model.

In our opinion, the issue of training (retraining) teachers of Physics to use the author's model of developing senior students' research competence in the process of teaching Physics is relevant and requires further scientific and methodical investigation.

**Checking statistical significance of differences
in levels of research competence technological component**

initial test				
	H	M	L	T _{it}
n ₁	570			
Q _{2i} (КГ)	141	331	52	
n ₂	524			
Q _{1i} (ЕГ)	130	327	113	
n ₁ Q _{2i} – n ₂ Q _{1i}	12250	17322	-29572	
Q _{1i} + Q _{2i}	271	658	165	
$\frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$	553736,2	456005,6	530001,9	5,155162
final special test				
	H	M	L	T _{ft}
n ₁	570			
Q _{2i} (КГ)	134	349	41	
n ₂	524			
Q _{1i} (ЕГ)	172	339	59	
n ₁ Q _{2i} – n ₂ Q _{1i}	-13748	21294	-7546	
Q _{1i} + Q _{2i}	306	688	100	
$\frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$	617671,6	659061,7	569421,2	6,181045

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ПЕРЕВІРКА ЕФЕКТИВНОСТІ ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ АВТОРСЬКОЇ МОДЕЛІ РОЗВИТКУ ДОСЛІДНИЦЬКОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ УЧНІВ ЛІЦЕЮ З ФІЗИКИ

Мета статті – представити результати формувального етапу психолого-педагогічного дослідження щодо визначення ефективності застосування авторської моделі розвитку дослідницької компетентності учнів ліцею в процесі викладання фізики.

Методологія дослідження: аналіз нормативно-правових документів України, стандартів, навчальних програм з фізики, підручників і навчальних посібників; синтез наявних у теорії і практиці навчання фізики підходів до розв'язання проблеми розвитку дослідницької компетентності учнів ліцею з фізики; спостереження за процесом навчання фізики учнів ліцею з метою визначення його закономірностей та можливостей удосконалення у напрямі формування дослідницької компетентності; діагностування рівня розвитку дослідницької компетентності учнів ліцею; тестування учнів; оцінювання результатів навчання; апробація запропонованої методичної системи розвитку дослідницької компетентності учнів ліцею у навчанні фізики; педагогічний експеримент; методи математичної статистики на етапі оброблення й узагальнення результатів педагогічного експерименту та формулювання висновків щодо підтвердження наукової новизни і практичного значення дослідження.

Наукова новизна. Представлено взаємозв'язок теоретичного та емпіричного підходів для практичного застосування у навчанні фізики; здійснено аналіз статистичних матеріалів дослідження на основі критеріїв *F*-Фішера, Пірсона (χ^2); окреслено напрямки подальшого розвитку теорії формування дослідницької компетентності ліцейств з фізики.

Висновки. Результати педагогічного експерименту показали ефективність запропонованих підходів для розвитку дослідницької компетентності учнів ліцею з фізики, а також педагогічну доцільність та ефективність методичної системи розвитку дослідницької компетентності з фізики учнів ліцеїв природничо-математичного напрямку диференціації.

Ключові слова: дослідницька компетентність, методична система формування дослідницької компетентності, навчально-методичний комплекс.

Стаття надійшла до редакції 29.09.2019

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